

ACCELERATED EVALUATION OF DEGRADATION BEHAVIOR OF GFRP IN HOT WATER AND ALKALINE SOLUTION

Masato Kasamori, Yoshinori Funada, Kaoru Awazu and Yoshio Watanabe
Industrial Research Institute of Ishikawa
Ro-1 Tomizu-machi, Kanazawa, Ishikawa 920-02, Japan
Yasushi Miyano
Materials System Research Laboratory, Kanazawa Institute of Technology
7-1 Ohgigaoka, Nonoichi, Kanazawa-south, Ishikawa 921, Japan

ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the degradation behavior of GFRP in hot water or alkaline solutions. Accelerated degradation tests are carried out at various constant temperatures from 100 to 200°C in hot water and alkaline aqueous solutions. The strength, modulus and weight of the GFRP change considerable according to time and temperature. The reciprocation law of exposing time and temperature holds for the degradation behavior of the GFRP. Therefore, the degradation behavior of the GFRP in hot water and alkaline solution above 100°C can be predicted based on the reciprocation law of time and temperature.

INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced plastics GFRP has been widely used in various environments. Accordingly, reliability over a long time period in various environments is required concerning the strength of GFRP. In many cases, however, it is difficult to execute long term tests, and accordingly predictive procedures for the degradation of GFRP strength in various environments have become a necessity. By the way, it is well known that the predictive procedure of long term deformation and strength of resins and FRP is based on the reciprocation law of time and temperature[1-4]. The purpose of this study is to evaluate accelerated degradation behavior that is strength, modulus and weight of GFRP in hot water and alkaline solutions, and then to demonstrate the applicability of the reciprocation law of time and temperature to the prediction of the degradation behavior.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The GFRP used consists of woven roving glass fabrics(Nippon sheet glass Co.Ltd., REW580) and an unsaturated polyester resin(Nippon shokubai Co.Ltd., Epolac G752-PTX). This GFRP was formed by lay up two sheets of roving and the resin was cast into a mold to about 1mm thickness. After hardening, These flat panels were cut into under 30mm length and 10mm width. Accelerated degradation tests were carried out at various constant temperatures from 100 to 200°C in hot water(distilled water),

10wt%NaOH and 10wt%KOH aqueous solution by using a decomposition bottle that consisted of stainless steel(outer) and teflon@(inner, inside diameter 30mm and height 40mm). The test conditions are shown in Table. The degradation of GFRP was evaluated by gravimetry and three point flexural tests that were conducted by the span 20mm and test speed 0.5mm/min in air at room temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The strengths of the GFRP at various exposing temperatures in hot water are shown in the left side of Fig.1. The strengths markedly decrease with progressing time and with increasing temperature. The smooth master curve of strength at a reference temperature $T_0=100^{\circ}\text{C}$ shown in the right side of this figure can be obtained by horizontally shifting the strength at various exposing temperatures. Therefore, this shows that the reciprocation law of time and temperature holds for the strength.

In regard to the modulus and change of weight, these also decrease remarkably with increasing time and temperature in the same manner as the strengths, and initiation and growth of cracks on the specimen surfaces are recognized corresponding to these results. Accordingly, respective master curves can be obtained as shown in Figs.2 and 3. Figure 4 shows the time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ required for composing the master curves of strength, modulus and weights. These shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ can be described by a line and agree with each other, and the activation energies are calculated at 56kJ/mol.

The weights of the GFRP in hot water are decreased by hydrolysis[5,6] of the unsaturated polyester resin used as the matrix in the GFRP. This activation energy can be obtained at 54kJ/mol from rate constant as shown in Fig.5, if this hydrolysis of the unsaturated polyester is assumed to the first order reaction. Both activation energies calculated from shift factors and rate constants agree well.

Concerning the 10wt%NaOH aqueous solution, cracks on the specimen surfaces are not recognized so much, however, swelling of the matrix resin is observed. The strengths of the GFRP at various exposing temperatures in 10wt%NaOH solution are shown in the left side of Fig.6. The strengths change remarkably more than in hot water, and decrease with progressing time and with increasing temperature. The smooth master curve of strength at $T_0=100^{\circ}\text{C}$ is shown in the right side of this figure. Therefore, this shows that the reciprocation law of time and temperature also holds for the strength in NaOH solution. Regarding the modulus and change of weight in NaOH solution, the reciprocation law of time and temperature also holds as shown in Figs.7 and 8. These shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ agree well with each other, and the activation energy is 38kJ/mol as shown in Fig.9. This value almost corresponds with the activation energy obtained at 42kJ/mol from rate constant of the hydrolysis based on an assumption of the first order reaction.

Furthermore, in case of the degradation of GFRP by using 10wt%KOH aqueous solution, swelling of the matrix resin is not observed, but dissolution is observed. However, the reciprocation law of time and temperature also holds for the strengths, modulus and change of weight in the same manner as the NaOH aqueous solution as shown in Figs.10 to 12. Then these activation energies are obtained at 40kJ/mol as shown in Fig.13.

Therefore, regarding the alkaline aqueous solutions, the strength and modulus decrease more rapidly than the change of weight. It was found that the alkaline aqueous solution accelerated the degradation of GFRP at lower temperature and shorter time than hot water, and the activation energy of degradation of GFRP decreases by the addition of alkalis. Furthermore, it is considered that the accelerated degradation method employing

the alkaline solutions seems to be possible for a chemical recycling method for GFRP waste.

CONCLUSION

Accelerated degradation tests are carried out at various constant temperatures from 100 to 200°C in hot water and alkaline aqueous solutions by using a decomposition bottle. The reciprocation law of exposing time and temperature holds for the degradation behavior of the GFRP above 100°C. Therefore, it is found that the degradation behavior of the GFRP can be predicted based on the reciprocation law of time and temperature. The alkaline aqueous solutions accelerated the degradation of GFRP at lower temperature and shorter time than hot water, and the activation energy of degradation decreases by the addition of alkalis.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y.Miyano, M.Kanemitsu and T.kunio, Time and Temperature Dependence of Flexural Strength in Transversal Direction of Fibers in CFRP, *Fibre Sci. and Tech.* **18**, 65–79(1983).
- [2] Y.Miyano, M.Kanemitsu, T.Kunio and H.A.Kuhn, A Study on Fracture Mechanisms of Unidirectional CFRP, *SAMPE J. Sep./Oct.* 33–40(1985).
- [3] Y.Miyano, M.Kanemitsu, T.Kunio and H.A.Kuhn, Role of Matrix Resin on Fracture Strengths of Unidirectional CFRP, *J. Comp. Mat.* **20**, 520–538(1986).
- [4] Y.Miyano and M.Kasamori, A Study on Long Term Creep Behavior for Matrix Epoxy Resin and CFRP, *Proceedings of the 1994 SEM Spring Conference on Experimental Mechanics*, 268–273(1994).
- [5] T.Hojo, K.Tsuda, K.Ogasawara and K.Mishima, The Effects of Stress and Flow Velocity on Corrosion Behavior of Vinyl Ester Resin and Glass Composites, *Proc. ICCM-IV, Vol.2*, 1017–1024(1982).
- [6] T.Hojo, K.Tsuda, K.Ogasawara and T.Takizawa, Corrosion Behavior of Epoxy and Unsaturated Polyester Resins in Alkaline Solution, *ACS Symp. Ser.* **322**, 314–326(1986).

Table Test conditions

Exposing time	hr (Hot water)	1, 2, 4, 6, 10, 24
	(Alkaline solution)	1/3, 2/3, 1, 2, 4, 6

Exposing temperature	°C	100, 125, 150, 175, 200

Fig.1 Master curve for flexural strength in H₂O.

Fig.2 Master curve for flexural modulus in H₂O.

Fig.3 Master curve for decrease of weight in H₂O.

Fig.4 Time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ for weight, strength and modulus in H₂O.

Fig.5 Arrhenius plot of change of weight ratio at various temperatures in H₂O.

Fig.6 Master curve for flexural strength in 10wt%NaOH aqueous solution.

Fig.7 Master curve for flexural modulus in 10wt%NaOH aqueous solution.

Fig.8 Master curve for decrease of weight in 10wt%NaOH aqueous solution.

Fig.9 Time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ for weight, strength and modulus in 10wt%NaOH aqueous solution.

Fig.10 Master curve for flexural strength in 10wt%KOH aqueous solution.

Fig.11 Master curve for flexural modulus in 10wt%KOH aqueous solution.

Fig.12 Master curve for decrease of weight in 10wt%KOH aqueous solution.

Fig.13 Time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ for weight, strength and modulus in 10wt%KOH aqueous solution.